

Research proposal

Machine learning in wave propagation modeling: From standard numerical methods to physics-informed neural networks in seismology

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Wave propagation plays a fundamental role in fields such as acoustics, electromagnetism, medicine, and geophysics. Standard numerical methods, such as the finite difference method, the finite element method, and the boundary element method, have been widely used to simulate wave propagation phenomena. However, they often involve high computational costs, especially in unbounded domains and inverse problems, which motivates the exploration of alternative solution techniques.

Unlike machine learning, whose rise has been more recent, the development of numerical methods has a consolidated trajectory of several decades, closely linked to the advancement of computing power and the automation of complex tasks, as well as to a mathematical foundation that provides theorems in diverse contexts (Rüde et al.; Burden et al., 2018; 2016). These methods have reached a high degree of maturity, with successful applications in numerous fields of science and engineering. However, the rapid evolution of machine learning opens new possibilities for addressing problems that have been extensively solved using standard numerical approaches. Based on the above, the following research question is posed:

How can machine learning constitute an alternative or a complement to applications related to seismic wave propagation?

In this context, it has been suggested that machine learning-based implementations can make applications more efficient, as is the case with wave propagation modeling, a task commonly addressed using standard numerical methods. The framework of this work is illustrated in Figure 1, where we propose to address the intersection between machine learning and wave propagation modeling, specifically in seismological applications. Accordingly, we formulate the research problem, along with the questions that guide the development of the study.

In particular, neural network-based algorithms have the ability to approximate functions by mapping input features to output targets in a data-driven manner. A version of the universal approximation theorem, as stated in Hornik et al. (1989), states that a feedforward neural network (FFNN) with a single hidden layer and a finite number of neurons can arbitrarily approximate any continuous function defined on a compact subset of the input space, provided that the activation function used is non-constant, bounded, and continuous. To illustrate this concept, consider the following function:

$$f(x) = x^3 + x^2 - x - 1.$$

To approximate this function, we divide the domain into N segments of equal length. In each segment, a contribution is defined based on the ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) activation function, so the segment is represented as:

$$g_i(x) = w_i \text{ReLU}(x - x_i^*) + y_i^{\text{offset}},$$

Figure 1. The intersection between machine learning, wave propagation modeling, and seismology, as a framework for our research.

where x_i^* is the start of the segment, w_i is the weight that determines the slope, and y_i^{offset} is a vertical offset that ensures continuity with the previous segments. The ReLU function ensures that the contribution of each segment starts in its corresponding region and is defined as:

$$\text{ReLU}(x - x_i^*) = \max(0, x - x_i^*),$$

generating a piecewise linear function in each segment. The figure [Figure 2](#) illustrates this process, showing how each ReLU-activated segment contributes to reconstructing the objective function. The complete approximation is obtained by combining all segments

$$f(x) \approx \hat{f}_i(x) = \sum_{i=1}^N g_i(x).$$

Each segment adds a ReLU-activated straight line that contributes locally to the shape of the function. Combining all the segments produces a piecewise approximation that captures the structure of $f(x)$.

Thus, machine learning has become a useful numerical tool for modeling systems governed by physical laws and described by partial differential equations ([Cuomo et al., 2022](#)), where the function to be approximated corresponds to the variable of interest. Machine learning-based methods offer significant advantages in terms of evaluation speed and adaptability, as they can be adjusted to different environmental configurations, boundary conditions, or data types without requiring a complete reformulation of the physical model. Furthermore, they are efficient in contexts where equation-based models are costly or difficult to construct, positioning them as a high-potential tool. However, they also have significant limitations, such as their reduced physical interpretability ([Zhang et al., 2020](#)).

One technique that seeks to preserve the advantages of machine learning while incorporating explicit physical knowledge is the use of Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) ([Raissi et al., 2019](#)). These have been used in various problems described by differential equations, but challenges remain when comparing their performance with standard methods due to differences in their formulation and computational approach.

Figure 2. Approximation of an objective function using a hidden single-layer neural network with varying numbers of neurons. The gray curve indicates the original function, while the blue curves show the approximations obtained by gradually increasing the number of neurons. The black curve is the final approximation with the total number of neurons.

PINNs also offer the possibility of addressing inverse problems (Raissi et al.; Haghighat et al.; Hao et al., 2020; 2021; 2023), in which the physical parameters of the model are inferred from experimental observations. This approach is particularly valuable in seismology, where subsurface characterization requires methods capable of leveraging observational information and physical wave propagation models. Thus, PINNs emerge as an alternative for efficiently estimating parameters.

The use of experimental observation data introduces additional challenges, such as noise in the measurements and an increase in the dimensionality of the problem. Therefore, this study proposes to investigate methods that integrate machine learning models into uncontrolled seismological problems, understood as those that go beyond the simplified cases used for evaluating the methods. The objective is to address more realistic and complex scenarios. Based on this general scenario, the following specific research questions guide the investigation:

1. What machine learning techniques have been applied to model wave propagation in the context of seismology?
2. How do modern machine learning-based approaches to solving PDEs compare with standard numerical methods?
3. To what extent can PINNs efficiently estimate the physical parameters of the model from seismic observations, while maintaining accuracy comparable to that of standard inversion methods?
4. How can machine learning-based approaches be scaled to leverage data from seismological problems in uncontrolled contexts?

These questions shape our research problem, which focuses on evaluating the role of machine learning techniques in modeling seismic wave propagation, as well as their viability as complementary or alternative tools to standard numerical methods.

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